

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Environmental costs of wheat production in Germany: effect of crop diversification and input reduction

Although conventional wheat cultivation is very efficient in terms of yield, it causes considerable environmental pollution due to the intensive use of chemicals. In this context, it is important to find alternatives that strike a balance between economic efficiency and environmental protection. This study analyzes the sustainability of agricultural practices such as crop diversification and reducing the use of chemicals, and their environmental costs (€ in impact per € gross margin for farmers). The aim is to provide valuable information to help policy makers promote more sustainable agricultural practices.

To conduct this analysis, an environmental cost-benefit analysis (e-CBA) based on life cycle assessment was performed to

compare three strategies in monetary terms: (T1) conventional production, (T2) extensive production without cover crops and (T3) diversified extensive production with clover. The results show that although conventional production has the lowest environmental costs due to its high production efficiency, it still presents high values (0.51 €/€). However, diversification with clover offers a more balanced approach where environmental costs are only 3% higher, suggesting that diversification with clover can reduce environmental impacts without significant effects on economic efficiency. Finally, the extensive strategy generates the highest environmental costs (+24%) due to its low production yields.

1. Environmental costs (€ per € gross margin for the farmer) for each tested practice.

KEYWORDS

Environmental costs, impacts, wheat cultivation, extensive farming, crop diversification

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